

DESORPTION ISOTHERMS AND DRYING KINETICS OF GROUND NEEM SEEDS WETTED WITH ORGANIC SOLVENTS

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ABSTRACT

The desorption isotherms and characteristic drying curves of ground neem seeds wetted with organic solvents were experimentally determined. The wetted material is obtained as intermediate byproduct during the manufacture of a biodegradable pesticide from neem seeds in a two step leaching process. Equilibrium isotherms of seeds wetted separately with the single solvents hexane and ethanol respectively were determined by a dynamic method. The characteristic drying curves for the two single solvents were obtained in a tunnel dryer. The influence of solute content in the solid upon drying kinetics was also examined. These equilibrium and kinetic data represent a useful information to aid the design of the dryer and recovery system required for the processing of neem seeds.

INTRODUCTION

During the manufacture of a biodegradable natural liquid insecticide, ground seeds of the neem tree (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) are first leached with hexane to extract oil, and subsequently with ethanol to obtain an ethanolic solution of the insecticide. After each leaching step, the solvent retained by the solid must be removed. A preliminary leaching study performed by Ramírez (1996), at pilot plant scale, indicates that as much as 80 kg of hexane and 70 kg of ethanol may be lost for every 100 kg of fresh seeds to be processed. Therefore, to avoid losses of valuable solvents and environmental pollution, the removal of the solvents from the ground seeds in a dryer and its subsequent recovery by condensation would be desirable. An adequate design of a dryer to remove the solvents requires knowledge about drying kinetics

and equilibrium data of the ground seeds wetted with each solvent. Apart from the influence of the solid, the removal of the solvents will be influenced by the presence of the non-volatile solute (oil or insecticide) since the solvent retained by the solid will normally not be completely free from solute after each leaching step. The objectives of this work were to obtain equilibrium data and to study the drying kinetics of ground neem seeds wetted separately with hexane and ethanol, as well as the influence of solute content and gas temperature on the drying rates.

THEORY

Desorption Isotherms

Desorption isotherms represent equilibrium moisture content of the solid as a function of gas humidity. Experimental isotherms for a variety of biological materials have been reported by Iglesias et al. (1982). Several of the empirical and semi-empirical relationships proposed to fit experimental data have been summarized by Chirife et al. (1978), Papadakis et al. (1993) and Park et al. (1996).

Characteristic Drying Curve

To describe the solid-side-controlled drying prevailing during the falling rate period, the drying rate N_v , can be represented as follows:

$$N_v = f(\Phi)K_y(Y_s - Y_g) \quad (1)$$

The expression for the relative drying rate, $f = N_v/N_w$, as a function of the characteristic moisture content, $\Phi = (X - X_e)/(X_c - X_e)$, is obtained from experimental data for each material. Both, the critical moisture content, X_c , and the drying rate for constant period, N_w , are obtained from drying rate curves and the equilibrium moisture content, X_e , from desorption isotherms.

Effect of solute on drying kinetics

The presence of a non volatile solute reduces the vapor pressure of the solvents, and affects the mass and heat transport in the solid. Therefore a reduction in the drying rate is expected when residual solutes are part of the moisture. According to Lee et al. (1994) the constant rate period tends to disappear, and no constant temperature profiles are obtained, at high solute concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

Raw material

Water free ground neem seeds, in a range of 0.335 to 1.6 mm, were used in the experiments. The composition of this material was: 49.7% oil, 18.0% insecticide and 32.3% non soluble solid matrix.

Desorption Isotherms

Desorption isotherms were determined for free solute seeds and the corresponding leaching solvent. Equilibrium data were obtained by a dynamic method with a constant and low gas flow. The closed

system shown in Figure 1 consists of two chambers immersed in separated thermostats. Nitrogen was saturated in a evaporation chamber, and then the gaseous mixture equilibrated with wet solid in a desorption chamber. The solid was placed in a grid of diameter 104 mm and 8 mm in depth. Sample weight was recorded with a precision balance (± 1 mg). Different relative humidities in the sample chamber, at temperature T2, were obtained by changing the temperature T1, in the humidification chamber. The relative humidity, Ψ , was calculated as: $\Psi = P_v^o 1 / P_v^o 2$. Saturation vapor pressure of the solvent, $P_v^o 1$ and $P_v^o 2$, were calculated by Wagner equation (Reid, 1987).

The equations reviewed by Papadakis et al. (1993) and Park et al. (1996) were tested for fitting the experimental results of X_e vs. Ψ . Fitness was evaluated by mean relative deviation modulus:

$$E = \frac{100}{n_e} \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \frac{|VE - VP|}{VE} \quad (2)$$

where n_e is the number of experimental data and VE and VP are experimental and predicted value, respectively. Equations providing values of E less than 10% were considered a good fitting model.

Figure 1. Desorption isotherms experimental equipment.

Drying Kinetics

Different solute contents in the moist solid were obtained by leaching the seeds in a soxhlet extractor, as indicated in table 1. As the insecticide is not miscible with hexane, it can be regarded as part of the inert solid in the experiments with hexane. Free oil seeds were used in all the experiments with ethanol.

Table 1. Solute Content in Drying Experiments (Inert Solid Basis).

	Solvent	Hexane	Ethanol
Level	Extraction time, h	Oil Content kg/kg	Insect. Content kg/kg
low	12	0	0
medium	3	0.38	0.33
high	0	0.99	0.56

Experiments were performed in a wind-tunnel dryer. Dehumidified air at 1 m/s, was heated by electrical resistances. The drying rate curves for both solvents and all solute contents, were determined at air temperature 40, 60 and 80°C ($\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). The relative drying rate curves were calculated only for the two free solute systems. Wet solid was placed in a circular tray, 64 mm internal diameter and 7 mm depth, suspended from an analytical balance (precision 0.1 mg). The sample weight, W_t , was recorded periodically to calculate the solvent content of the ground seeds by:

$$X = \frac{W_t - W_i}{W_i} \quad (3)$$

The mass of inert solid, W_i , was obtained by drying the samples during 18 hours in a oven at 60°C and subtracting the mass of solute. The evaporation rate was then calculated as:

$$N_v = - \frac{W_i dX}{A_s dt} \quad (4)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Desorption Isotherms

The results of desorption experiments for both solvents, carried out at 30°C, and the three best fitting curves are represented in Figure 2. Parameters were estimated by non linear regression. Five models satisfied the fitness criterion for hexane-neem (Table 2). Ethanol-neem isotherm was only adjusted by Peleg equation. With both solvents the liquid content of the equilibrium was relatively low. The values were lowest for hexane.

Figure 2. Desorption isotherms of ground neem seeds with different solvents.

Best results with Peleg model: $X_e = K1 * \Psi^{n1} + K2 * \Psi^{n2}$.

Table 2. Results of Correlation for Desorption Isotherms Data.

System	Model	Error %	Constants			
			K1=0.1027	K2=0.1794	n1=0.3744	n2=22.6967
Hexane - Neem Seeds	Peleg	2.1				
	BET	4.1	XM=25	C=1.009	n=0.0008	-
	Oswin	5.4	A=0.0758	B=0.2378	-	-
	Halsey	5.6	A=0.3626	B=0.3035	-	-
Ethanol - Neem Seeds	Henderson	9.5	A=1.0638	B=0.4301	-	-
	Peleg	4.8	K1=0.2295	K2=2.5897	n1=0.6214	n2=16.2469

Characteristic Drying Curves

The characteristic drying curves for the remotion of hexane and ethanol, as well as the proposed polynomial equations, are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Characteristic drying curves of ground neem seeds. Air velocity = 1 m/s. Polynomial equations: Hexane-neem: $f = 8.642\Phi^5 - 24.227\Phi^4 + 23.971\Phi^3 - 9.945\Phi^2 + 2.588\Phi - 0.036$
 Ethanol-neem: $f = 7.927\Phi^6 - 23.849\Phi^5 + 19.209\Phi^4 + 1.498\Phi^3 - 6.485\Phi^2 + 2.707\Phi - 0.016$

Effect of solute in the drying kinetics

Drying rate curves for the systems hexane-oil-neem seeds and ethanol-insecticide-neem seeds are presented in Figure 4. An initial cooling period was observed for both systems. For solid wetted with hexane, the constant rate period tends to disappear as solute content and gas temperature increased. The effect on the system containing ethanol is less pronounced. This is mainly due to the lower initial drying rate of ethanol compared to hexane.

Figure 4. Influence of solute content on the drying of ground neem seeds.

In Figure 4, simulation results obtained by solving mass and energy balances that describe the drying process have been included. In these calculations, the relative drying rate previously estimated, and the reduction of vapor pressure with the solute content have been considered. From these results, it is clear that the relative drying rate obtained in a solute free solid is not able to provide a satisfactory description of the drying process when solutes are present. Furthermore, the good agreement in the solute free solid was only possible when the correction provided by the relative drying rate was also applied to the heat flux by convection. It is evident that the reduction of drying rate provoked by the diminution of relative drying rate with liquid content that occurs below the critical point is counteracted by a larger driving force for mass transfer, due to an increase in solid temperature. Consequently, simulated drying rate curves without a corresponding correction for heat transfer, exhibit a slower diminution compared to experimental curves. The asymmetrical treatment of mass and heat transfer involved in the concept of relative drying rate represents a serious weakness when it is applied to simulations. Resistance against heat transfer within the solid would exist, for instance, if a receding evaporation front with a evaporation temperature lower than surface temperature would appear as the solid dries out. However, to account for the resistance against heat transfer in the same way that the resistance against mass transfer is a simplification since the processes of internal heat and mass transfer will not be necessarily analogous due to the heterogeneous nature of the wet solid.

CONCLUSIONS

Relative drying rates curves for ground neem seeds wetted with ethanol and hexane have been expressed by polynomial equations. Desorption isotherms data for both systems are well described by Peleg model. The presence of non-volatile solutes affects the drying rate by reducing its magnitude and shortening the duration of the constant rate period. The extent of these effects depends on the concentration of solutes and their chemical nature. The relative drying rate obtained in a solute free solid does not provide a satisfactory description of the drying process when solutes are present. Even in a solute free solid, the concept can fail due to the absence of a proper treatment of heat transfer.

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NOTATION

A_s	Sample surface	m^2
f	Relative drying rate	-
K_y	Mass transfer coefficient	kg/m^2s
N_v	Drying rate per surface of solid	kg/m^2s
N_w	Drying rate during constant rate period	kg/m^2s
P	Pressure	bar
T	Temperature	K
u	linear velocity	m/s
W	Weight	kg
X	Average solvent content of the inert solid	kg/kg

Greek letters

Φ	Characteristic moisture content	-
Ψ	Relative humidity	-

Subscripts

c	critical value	e	equilibrium value
g	gas	i	inert solid

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